

ID 1020

EFFECT OF CARBON CONTENT ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE OF IN SITU TiCp/Fe COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: In this paper, two kinds of TiC particulate reinforced ferrous matrix with different carbon contents were synthesized by a liquid state in situ process, and their microstructures were studied by means of transmission electron microscope and X-ray diffractometer. Results show that the particle reinforcement is non-stoichiometric TiC_xN_{1-x} , in which X value depended on the carbon content of raw material. It seems that higher carbon content helps to refrain the formation of Fe_2Ti phase.

KEYWORDS : Carbon Content, Microstructure, In situ Composite

INTRODUCTION

Based on the superhard titanium carbide reinforcement and various matrix structures of steel and cast irons, the TiC/iron-based alloy composites are a unique group of metal matrix composites(MMCs) which retain the properties even at high temperature with the required low friction for both static and dynamic components. However, the fabrication processing of this kind of MMCs by conventional powder metallurgy has several limitations for the homogeneity of the materials. In recent studies, solidification processing has emerged as one of the most economical and versatile techniques to produce MMCs. The possibility of producing TiC-ferrous matrix composites through the liquid route has been studied(1-6). Titanium carbide particles were formed in iron solution by a reaction between carbon and titanium after casting a supersaturated Fe-Ti-C melt, causing precipitation of the TiC particles(1,2), or by a reaction between graphite and Fe-Ti alloy, between Ti and Fe-C alloy, or between Fe-Ti and Fe-C alloy(3-6). The effect of cooling rate on the ripening kinetics of

carbide particle has also been studied(1,2). However, little work has been done on the microstructures of these MMCs, which is necessary to understand and control the process. In the present study the microstructure of cast ferrous matrix composite reinforced by TiCp synthesized with liquid state in situ process has been studied by means of transmission electron microscope(TEM) and X-ray diffraction(XRD), and the effect of carbon content of raw materials was discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Pig iron and ferro titanium were used for the synthesis of composite. The compositions(wt%) of these raw materials were shown in Table 1. The amounts of pig iron and ferro titanium to use were calculated respectively to get two kinds of Fe-Ti-C alloy, namely HC composition(2.5Ti, 3.2C, 2.5Si, balance Fe, wt%) and LC composition(3.0Ti, 1.5C, 2.5Si, balance Fe, wt%). The synthesis of the composite was carried out in an induction furnace in the air. Pre-distributed ferro titanium and pig iron were melted in induction furnace. When melt temperature reached the reaction temperature of 1600° C, it was held as long as 5mins. By means of physi-chemical action within the melt, dispersed TiC particle reinforcements were manufactured. During the holding period of melt, covering agent was added to prevent oxidation of titanium. Finally the melt was poured into resin sand mold to form specimens of ϕ 10mm \times 100mm.

Table 1

Compositions of the raw materials used in the synthesis of Fe-TiC composites

	C	Ti	S	P	Si	Mn	Fe
Pig iron	4.13	-----	<0.03	<0.03	1.21	0.16	balance
Ferro-Titanium	0.084	40.56	0.022	0.47	-----	-----	balance

The phases formed after in situ synthesis process were identified by X-ray diffraction(XRD) using nickel-filtered Cu K α radiation. Microstructural and compositional examinations were carried out in a JEOL JEM200C transmission electron microscopy(TEM) at 200KV. An energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy(EDX) with beryllium window which can detect light elements such as carbon and nitrogen was linked to the microscope. Samples for TEM were prepared by standard methods involving mechanical grinding, polishing and dimpling followed by ion milling of foil to perforation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 shows the interface morphology between reinforcement and matrix in HC specimen. As we can see from Fig.1a, interface between reinforcement and matrix is clean and no other product is formed. Periphery matrix is typical pearlite. While EDX spectrum shows that its composition(at,%) is 52.78Ti, 22.82C, 24.40N, which means that the produced reinforcement is non-stoichiometric Ti(C,N). It can also be expressed as TiC_xN_{1-x} . It is well known that

C/N ratio can be changed in a range while TiC_xN_{1-x} remain its crystal structure. We know that both TiC and TiN have f.c.c. lattice, and their lattice constant is 0.433nm and 0.423nm respectively. If we assume the constant of TiC_xN_{1-x} linearly changes with the change of X value. Then the constant of $TiC_{0.5}N_{0.5}$ can be calculated as 0.428nm. In fact, by using a high angle XRD peak(Fig.2), the precise constant of $TiC_{0.5}N_{0.5}$ in HC is also measured as 0.428nm. Thus, the particle reinforcement in HC specimen can be written as $TiC_{0.5}N_{0.5}$.

Fig.3a shows the interface morphology between reinforcement and matrix in LC specimen. It is noticed that carbon content also have some effect on the microstructure of periphery matrix under the same condition. In comparison with HC specimen, the amount of cementite in periphery matrix in LC specimen is much less due to its low carbon content. It only resumes as pearlite microstructure in area away from particle reinforcement. As EDX spectrum shows that particle composition(at,%) is 56.80Ti, 14.32C, 28.87N, which means that it is also non-stoichiometric, it can be expressed as $TiC_{0.3}N_{0.7}$.

Apart from Ti(C,N) particles, a strip phase can be observed in LC specimen, as shown in Fig.3c. EDX spectrum shows that its composition(at,%) is 60.34Fe, 39.66Ti. Lattice parameters measured from diffraction pattern also corresponds with Fe_2Ti phase. So this phase is proved to be Fe_2Ti . Meanwhile, as no Fe_2Ti phase can be observed in HC specimen. It seems that higher carbon content helps to refrain the formation of Fe_2Ti phase.

It should be pointed out that Fe_2Ti phase is not common in LC specimen and no corresponding peak of the phase is found in its XRD spectrum, indicating that the amount of Fe_2Ti phase in LC specimen is small.

Next we shall have a brief discussion of the difference in the microstructure between samples HC and LC. In the present study, reaction took place in the system which contained Fe-Ti-C alloy system and nitrogen atoms in a certain condition of the process. As titanium is an intensive carbonitride-forming element, it can be understood that part of nitrogen participated in the reaction to form Ti(C,N) in the air environment. Nevertheless, as reacting parent alloy is in liquid state in reacting temperature, carbon dissolved in the melt is the active carbon[C], it has priority for [C] to react with Ti to form Ti(C,N), since chemical reactions in the system is determined by both thermodynamic and kinetic factors. Therefore, it is quite possible that carbon content of particle reinforcement is different when the carbon content of corresponding raw material is different.

From Fe-Ti diagram, Ti and Fe can react to produce two types of compounds, Fe_2Ti and

TiFe. By thermodynamical calculation, Gibbs formation free energy for possible phases in Ti-C-Fe system has been found(7). The results showed that most possibly formed and stably existed phase was TiC, next was Fe_2Ti phase. These thermodynamical computation results were obtained in the equilibrium condition, while in situ reaction process was a nonequilibrium process under nonequilibrium condition. So it is postulated that as the Ti/C ratio is too low, carbon content is not enough to react with titanium to form TiC or Ti(C,N), thus excess titanium reacts with iron to form Fe_2Ti phase. While in HC specimen with higher carbon content, C/Ti ratio is enhanced, so no Fe_2Ti phase is observed in its microstructure. Therefore, carbon content can be appropriately raised to keep an appropriate C/Ti ratio. It will help to restrain formation of harmful Fe_2Ti compound.

CONCLUSIONS

In the in situ synthesized TiC particle reinforced iron matrix composite, the particle reinforcement is non-stoichiometric TiC_xN_{1-x} , in which X value depended on the carbon content of raw material. Small amount of Fe_2Ti phase is observed in specimen with low carbon content, while no Fe_2Ti phase is observed in specimen with high carbon content. It seems that higher carbon content helps to refrain the formation of Fe_2Ti phase.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research has been jointly supported by the State Key Laboratory of Advanced Technology for Materials Composing in Wuhan University of Technology and the State Key Laboratory of Metal Matrix Composites in Shanghai Jiao Tong University.

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Fig.1 Interface between reinforcement and matrix in HC specimen
 a)bright field image b)EDX spectrum of reinforcement

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 a)bright field image b)EDX spectrum

Fig.2 Precise measurement of the lattice constant
 of TiC_xN_{1-x} in HC specimen by XRD

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Fig.3 Reinforcement and Fe₂Ti phase in LC specimen
 a) reinforcement b)EDX spectrum of reinforcement
 c) Fe₂Ti phase d) EDX spectrum of Fe₂Ti phase

Fig.3 Reinforcements and Fe₂Ti phase in LC specimen
 a)reinforcements b) EDX spectrum of reinforcement
 b) Fe₂Ti phase d) EDX spectrum of Fe₂Ti phase